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COTTON FIBER RATING, INNOVATION CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS, PROSPECTS FOR COOPERATION OF FARMS AND CLUSTERS

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Abstract: The article shows the results of six varieties of cotton seed breeding varieties grown by supplying them with high yields with advanced agrotechnical methods, production of high-quality cotton fiber from cultivated raw cotton, introduction of new technologies, as well as the classification of the resulting cotton fiber based on the international universal ISO standard, as well as conducted scientific and practical research in determining the rating place of the fiber.

Key words: raw cotton, fiber, joint, farmer, fiber rating, quality, genie machine, pneumomechanical women, textiles, micronair, research, laboratory system HVI, selection type.

Class method -Today, cotton seeds of many breeding varieties are planted on the territory of the republic. For example, while varieties S 65-24 and Namangan-77 have been widely planted for more than 35 years, such breeding varieties as Andijan-35, Andijan-36, glossy-1, glossy-2, glossy-3, Namangan-34 are relatively new varieties. In addition, our breeders create a large number of breeding varieties, conduct scientific and practical research and conduct pilot work.

Experts of the spinning enterprises of the Kalava cotton textile cluster, as well as other spinning enterprises, pay more attention to such quality indicators as the length of cotton fibers (Len - high average length), microneedles (microfibre maturation and thinness, thickness), as well as the percentage of short fibers in fibers (SFI-short fiber index). This is a true and necessary condition, with special emphasis on the optimal state of the microneedle, which is 4.0, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3,.

Cotton farms, on the other hand, want to plant cotton varieties that are primarily fertile, resistant to diseases, have a short growing season and are low in water. Grief in this case is considered quite correct and understandable.

First of all, the production of cotton fibers began with the determination of

quality indicators in the HVI laboratory system in accordance with the International Universal ISO Standard.

According to 10 quality indicators, based on a 10-point system, the rating position of the fibers of the grade 6-N selection was as follows:

Table 1.

Fiber rating position	Selection variety of fibers.	Total points awarded under the HVI system.
1.	Glossy-2	91
2.	C 65-24	74
3.	Namangan-77	70
4.	Andijan -35	64
5.	Namangan -34	57
6.	C 82-86	56

Selection varieties of cotton fibers recorded according to this table 1; Quality indicators were determined based on the international ISO standard such as Len-high average fiber length, UNF-longitudinal uniformity, SFI-short fiber index, Mic-microneedle, Elg-elongation at discontinuity, Str-specific elongation strength, Rd-beam return coefficient, Tb-fiber yellowing rate, Trask-impurity code, Cnt-amount of impurities, and Area-dirty mixing area.

From the table, it can be seen that the newly created glossy-2 selection grade was given 1st place in the retting relay due to the increased uniformity of the fiber in terms of high length and length due to the gene nakautized. Despite being a relatively old variety, it is seen that the S 65-24 and Namangan-77 varieties have not lost their former quality indicators. Despite being a relatively new Variety, the varieties Andijan-35, Namangan-34 and S 82-86 ranked fourth, fifth and sixth, respectively.

Scientific and practical research is also being carried out in the direction of setting ranking positions on other selection varieties being planted in the Republic.

It is known that in the separation of fibers and seeds from cotton, that is, in the Jinning of cotton, saw gin machines are

used for medium-fiber cotton, and roller gin machines for thin-fiber cotton.

In existing saw gin machines, Jinned cotton fibers were found to be quality indicators in the USA HVI laboratory system according to the 6 different selection varieties shown in Table 1. In order to study the extent to which mechanical damage is caused to the natural quality of fiber and seeds in the process of cotton ginning, according to the 6 different selection varieties of cotton listed in the table above, fibers from the seed were separated by hand without mechanical damage, that is, fibers from the seed. The separated fibers were tested in the HVI laboratory system. The saw was compared with the quality of the fibers from the Gin machine.

The comparison table showed that the cutting of fibers in the Len-high average length on a saw gin machine is on average 3-5 percent in terms of 6 homogeneous selection varieties under consideration. This pointer also has a corresponding negative effect on the percentage of SFI-short fibers in the fiber content.

In the Arrali jin machine, a condition not yet known to science has been discovered, that is, the Str-specific elongation force of fibers in the raw material chamber is decreasing by 2.0-2.4

Gs/Tex. It will be necessary to study the cause.

From 2016, work began on the creation of a fundamentally new "Pneumomechanical gin machine" at NamIET to separate fibers and seeds from

cotton. A small experimental copy of the new gin was prepared and scientific and practical work was carried out, the fibers obtained were tested in the HVI system. (Selection variety glossy-2, I/1).

Table 2.

The results of the comparison were as follows:

No	Fiber HVI is the name and designation of quality indicators in the laboratory system.	Quality indicators of fibers that come out of the sawed gin.	Fiber quality from the experimental machine of the new pneumomechanical gin	Fiber natural quality indicators
1	2	3	4	5
1.	Len -Upper Half Mean Length. dyuym.mm	1.14 28.9 mm (34.1 mm)	1.22 31.0 mm (36.6 mm)	1.34 34.0 mm (40.1 mm)
2.	Unf -Uniformity Index, %	84.51	84.80	85.10
3.	SFI- Short Fiber Index. Index of short fibers,%	7.75	5.2	2.7
4.	Mic.- Micronare.	4.6	4.1	4.2
5.	Elg. - Elongation, %	6.89	7.30	7.0
6.	Str -Strength Specific break strength, Gs/teks	33.20	34.30	35.60
7.	Rd- Reflectance. Beam return coefficient	77.03	79.80	82.60
8.	Tb -Yellowness.	8.86	6.80	8.10
9.	Trash -Trash Code.	3.9	4.0	4.0
10.	Cnt -Trash Count.	10	6	4
11.	Area- Trash Area. %	0.6	0.8	0.4

It will be possible to conduct a very in-depth analysis in accordance with Table 2. For example, the state of changes in Len fibers of a higher average length indicates a much more serious condition. Taking into account the fact that the existing saw gin production machine causes serious

mechanical damage to the fibers, the creation of another new, innovative gin production machine becomes extremely relevant.

Len-the change in the diagram of the high average length of the fibers:

It is known that the percentage of short fibers in fibers is understood to be those that are shorter than 0.5 inches (12.7 mm) in length. Such fibers do not reach in the combing machine, that is, these short fibers do not reach the spinning machine.

The fact that the existing saw machine cuts the fibers in the machine and exceeds the percentage of short fibers remains a problematic situation. The natural quality of the fibers has also been proven in studies in which short fibers account for about 2.4-2.7% in holti. This condition was taken into account in the production of high-quality fibers.

In low-grade fibers, that is, grade IV-V fibers, short fibers account for 14-20%.

In low-grade, i.e., IV-V grade fibers, short fibers are 14-20%.

Innovative projects on achieving high quality and high productivity are also being prepared in cooperation with cotton farms and textile clusters. That is, in order to increase the cotton dressing to 70-75 centners, it will be necessary, first of all, to organize poultry farming on farms, to prepare it for humus by rotting manure, and to land in early spring. It will be necessary that the cotton drip irrigation system is also carried out by farms in cooperation with clusters. It is also ensured that the benefits from poultry and eggs cover much more costs, as well as the creation of new jobs.

Significant work is also being carried out by scientists from the Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology in order to significantly improve the quality of lint obtained during linting. The main goal is to separate and improve the quality of down in accordance with the standard requirements of Type A (Grade I, Grade II, higher, medium, dirty grade) and Type B (Grade I, Grade II, higher, medium, dirty grade).

First of all, in this direction, a device is being tested on a 5 hp linter machine to improve the quality of down by cleaning pollen on vibrating mesh surfaces. The next task was to create a vacuum cleaner and a type separation machine.

The first scientific and practical studies on a sharp improvement in the quality of down began to give their positive result. That is, moles from the dirty class are transferred to a higher class. In turn, type II switches to fluffy I-NAV. The price of torque, which is determined on the stock exchange, respectively, also rises sharply. Types A and B remain in place. Due to this, the length of the fluff does not depend on the efficiency of cleaning.

One of the real scientific and technical achievements of recent years at the Institute was the creation of a large industrial copy of the "device for extracting pure spinning fibers from industrial cotton

waste”, which received high results. That is, in industry, it was possible to obtain an additional 5-5.5% of cotton fiber. Currently, measures are being taken to commercialize innovative devices worldwide and in tabular format.

Conclusion. 1) first of all, it is an urgent issue to determine their natural quality indicators on the selection varieties of cotton in the US HVI laboratory system and determine the position of retting.

2) the creation of the innovative device “creation of a Pneumomechanical gin machine” in relation to the Jinning of cotton in a new way is a huge scientific and technical achievement, which is receiving high results.

3) the project of obtaining 70-75 centners of cotton in cooperation with farms and cotton textile clusters is extremely relevant.

4) the successful start of innovative scientific and practical work in the direction of a sharp increase in the quality of fluff (lint) is also becoming relevant and significant.

5) the creation of an industrial copy of a pure, spinable fiber extraction device from industrial cotton waste is important to the economy, and its rapid commercialization will be extremely important.

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C O N T E N T S

PRIMARY PROCESSING OF COTTON, TEXTILE AND LIGHT INDUSTRY

A.Shodmonkulov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev

Analysis of load changes in the chain drive during the drying process of cotton falling from the longitudinal shelves of the drum..... 3

A.Xomidjonov

Influence and characteristics of drying mechanisms in leather production on the derma layer..... 8

J.Monnopov, J.Kayumov, N.Maksudov

Analysis of elastic fabrics for compression sportswear in the new assortment 13

S.Matismailov, K.Matmuratova, Sh.Korabayev, A.Yuldashev

Investigation of the influence of speed modes of the combined drum on the quality indicators of the tape..... 18

A.Shodmonkulov, K.Jumaniyazov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev

Determination of the geometric and kinematic parameters of the developed chain gear for the 2SB-10 dryer..... 23

R.Jamolov, A.Shodmonkulov, X.Yuldashev

Determination of dryer drum moisture extraction depending on its operating modes..... 27

A.Djuraev, K.Yuldashev, O.Teshaboyev

Theoretical studies on screw conveyor for transportation and cleaning of linter and design of constructive parameters of transmissions..... 29

S.Khashimov, Kh.Isakhanov, R.Muradov

Creation of technology and equipment for improved cleaning of cotton from small impurities..... 36

G.Juraeva, R.Muradov

The process of technical grades of medium staple cotton at gin factories and its analysis..... 40

I.Xakimjonov

Literature analysis on the research and development of the method of designing special clothes for workers of metal casting and metal processing enterprises..... 44

GROWING, STORAGE, PROCESSING AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS AND FOOD TECHNOLOGIES

A.Khodjiev, A.Choriev, U.Raximov

Improving the technology of production of functional nutrition juices..... 49

U.Nishonov

Research in beverage technology intended to support the functions of the cardiovascular system..... 53

Z.Vokkosov, S.Hakimov	
Development of new types of vegetable juices and beverages technology...	59
CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGIES	
M.Latipova	
Analysis of the current status of thermoelectric materials and technology for obtaining and manufacturing half-elements.....	66
G.Ochilov, I.Boymatov, N.Ganiyeva	
Physico-chemical properties of activated adsorbents based on logan bentonite.....	72
U.Nigmatov	
Simulation of heat transfer process in absorber channels.....	77
T.Abduxakimov, D.Sherkuziev	
Procurement of local raw materials complex fertilizers with nitrogen-phosphate-potassium containing moisture.....	84
P.Tojiyev, X.Turaev, G.Nuraliyev, A.Djalilov	
Study of the structure and properties of polyvinyl chloride filled with bazalt mineral.....	89
M.Yusupov	
Investigation of phthalocyanine diamidophosphate- copper by thermal analysis.....	95
L.Oripova, P.Xayitov, A.Xudayberdiyev	
Testing new activated coals AU-T and AU-K from local raw materials when filtration of the waste mdea at gazlin gas processing plant.....	101
N.Kurbanov, D.Rozikova	
Based on energy efficient parameters of fruit drying chamber devices for small enterprises.....	107
Sh.Xakimov, M.Komoliddinov	
Basic methods and technological schemes for obtaining vegetable oils.....	113
A.Boimirzaev, Z.Kamolov	
Size-exclusion chromatography of some polysaccharide derivatives from natural sources.....	117
MECHANICS AND ENGINEERING	
U.Erkaboev, N.Sayidov	
Dependence of the two-dimensional combined density of states on the absorbing photon energy in GaAs/AlGaAs at quantizing magnetic field.....	124
I.Siddikov, A.Denmumaxamadiyev, S.A'zamov	
Investigation of electromagnetic current transformer performance characteristics for measuring and controlling the reactive power dissipation of a short-circuited rotor synchronous motor.....	136
Sh.Kudratov	
Evaluation and development of diagnostics of the crankshaft of diesel locomotives.....	141

Z.Khudoykulov, I.Rakhmatullaev	
A new key stream encryption algorithm and its cryptanalysis.....	146
T.Mominov, D.Yuldoshev	
Coordination of the movement of transport types in areas with high passenger flow.....	157
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev, S.Baxritdinov	
Analysis of research results according to international standards.....	163
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev	
Cotton fiber rating, innovation current developments, prospects for cooperation of farms and clusters.....	168
F.Dustova, S.Babadzhanov.	
Calculation of the load on the friction clutch of the sewing machine.....	174
Z.Vafayeva, J.Matyakubova, M.Mansurova	
Improvement of the design of the shuttle drum in the sewing machine.....	179
A.Obidov, M.Vokhidov	
Preparation of a new structure created for sorting of ginning seeds.....	185
Sh.Mamajanov	
Carrying out theoretical studies of the cotton regenerator.....	192
ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION	
A.Khojaev	
Methodological issues of organizing internal audits and control of off-budget funds in higher education institutions.....	199
I.Nosirov	
Theoretical foundations of establishing new technologies on personal management system.....	203
Z.Mamakhanova, D.Ormonova	
Specific characteristics of uzbek national art of embroidery.....	209
A.Raximov, M.Khusainov, M.Turgunpulatov, S.Khusainov, A.Gaybullayev	
Energy-saving modes of the heat treatment of concrete.....	213
ECONOMICAL SCIENCES	
M.Bekmirzayev, J.Xolikov	
Prospects for the development of service industries.....	222
A.Ilyosov	
Organizational and economic mechanisms to support the export of industrial products: a comparative analysis of foreign experience and proposals.....	227
I.Foziljonov	
The importance of multiplier indicators in assessing the effectiveness of the cash flow of the enterprise.....	232
K.Kurpayanidi	
Innovative activity of business entities in the conditions of transformation: a retrospective analysis.....	238

Sh.Muxitdinov

Main characteristics of the risk management mechanism in manufacturing enterprises..... 248

Y.Najmiddinov

Green economy and green growth. initial efforts of sustainable development in Uzbekistan..... 252

E.Narzullayev

The methods for measuring the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship activity..... 259

E.Narzullayev

Analysis of the management and development of environmental social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan..... 265

F.Bayboboeva

Legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity..... 270

Z.Boltaeva

Foundations of neuromarketing strategy in industry..... 276

R.Rashidov

Issues of regional development of small business..... 281

Sh.Abdumurotov

Methodology for forecasting the competitiveness of an enterprise based on the Elliott wave principle..... 288

S.Goyipnazarov

Assessment of impact of artificial intelligence on labor market and human capital..... 299

A.Norov

Evolution of management science..... 307

K.Narzullayev

Investment process in the republic of Uzbekistan..... 317

Kh.Irismatov

Statistical analysis of assessment of the volume of the hidden economy in the republic of Uzbekistan..... 322
